

OSCAR Focus Groups on Knowledge Graph and Graph-based Recommender System Evaluation

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1. Introduction

In the scope of OSCAR project, the development of the knowledge graph structure and the graph-based recommender system has been carried out in collaboration with experts and content creators. This was to ensure that the algorithms logic was in-line with the needs of the target users, and the educational requirements that the eDeor platform has to fulfill. Experts feedback was also an essential part of the evaluation strategy, which included quantitative and qualitative measures to evaluate the performance and outcomes of the algorithms used for constructing the knowledge graph and the recommender system.

The inclusion of experts in the development and evaluation phases took the form of focus groups, which were arranged and conducted along three distinguishable phases: the conceptual phase of constructing the knowledge graph, the development of contextualized user profile, and the evaluation phase of the graph-based recommendation system.

- The first focus groups that were conducted during the conceptual development of the knowledge graph were oriented to survey the methods used by content creators for connecting educational materials to each other, and compare those approaches to the algorithmic approaches used for finding semantic relations among those materials.
- The conceptual phase of developing the recommendation system required a concrete definition of the user profile and the learning context, in order to enable the recommender system of accounting for the context of the learner when generating the learning path recommendation. To achieve a better understanding of the learning context, a focus group was also conducted with pedagogical experts, to adopt a pedagogically informed definition of the learning context and the contextual factors needed in the user profile.
- The last focus groups were intended to evaluate the final knowledge graph structure, as well as the logic and performance of the recommendation system. Those were conducted with experts and learners, who had no previous interaction with the eDeor platform, or the knowledge graph content.

In the following sections, the methodology and results of each of the above-mentioned focus groups are discussed in detail.

2. Focus groups on knowledge graph development

2.1. Background

These focus group took place after the conceptual framework development for the technical parts related to knowledge graph construction and recommendation algorithm. The focus groups were implemented to keep the technical development in line with the requirements from domain experts. Therefore, participants in the focus groups were the domain experts in the OSCAR project, who developed the first educational content on researcher mental health and career development.

Although all those focus groups were implemented to answer the same questions, multiple occurrences of the same discussion were needed to tailor the focus group towards the domain-specific content that each expert created in the system. Therefore, 5 participating experts were divided into three sub-groups, where each sub-group discussed the integration of their respective domain-specific content in the knowledge graph and the recommender system. The domains of the focus group discussions were:

- Researcher mental health
- Career development
- Food and drink processing

Demographically, focus group participants were from Portugal, Ireland, Belgium and Germany.

2.2. Methodology

The focus groups were planned and executed according to the following protocol:

- **Participants:** 5 experts.
- **Dates and time:** **Group1:** 16.02.2022, 11:00-12:30 – **Group2:** 16.03.2022, 11:00-12:30 – **Group3:** 24.03.2022, 09:00-10:30
- **Duration:** 1:30 hours
- **Pre-requisites:** Being a content creator on eDeor platform, Familiar with OSCAR-related content.
- **Location:** Online (Zoom video conference)
- **Moderator:** Hasan Abu-Rasheed (USI)
- **Digital formats used:** Concept Board, MS-PowerPoint

- **Procedure:**

1. *Welcome and explanation of the focus group's goal (10 min).*

2. *Knowledge graph – relation evaluation (30 min):*

Participants have examined a group or relations between courses and topics. They evaluated the correctness of those relations from the perspective of their own domain. Participants also drew new relations when needed to connect other educational content. Participants also discussed the length of relations and the transitive property of connecting courses and topics to other relevant ones.

3. *Learning path ordering and contextualization (40 min):*

Participant examined three learner stories, representing three different learning contexts. Participants then were provided with a group of learning materials to order in learning path, which they would recommend in each context.

Learner stories were phrased as follows:

Learner 1: is a university student in the psychology department. The learner is in the second year of the study (they have some knowledge of the field of stress management). They are facing difficulties in managing the master thesis, along with the remaining exams they have, which is causing them to be stressed most of the time. The learner was introduced to eDoer and wants to look for a way to help them handle the situation.

Learner 2: is a bachelor student in mathematics. The learner is facing a problem with their supervisor. This problem is causing them to be stressed and less motivated to continue the study. The learner thinks that their stress is making the problem with the supervisor even worse, and therefore they want to use eDoer to look for a possible solution to this current mental state.

Learner 3: is a hobbyist who likes to get know the field of psychology. They have no previous experience, but they wish to use eDeor to get some information about the topic. They searched for psychology related skills, and they found "stress management", so they decided to check it out.

4. Summary and final thoughts (10 min).

- **Questions discussed by the participants:**

1. Are of the following skills and topics related, directly or indirectly, to each other? and why?
2. Given the three learner stories, how would you order the following content in three learning paths corresponding to each story?
3. What are the main factors that you used to select the elements and order of the learning path?
4. How do you evaluate the following, automatically generated, learning path?

2.3. Findings

The discussion for the previous questions resulted in highlighting several important points to be considered in the development of the knowledge graph and the recommendation system. The following input was provided by the participants for each of the questions:

2.3.1. Are of the following skills and topics related, directly or indirectly, to each other? and why?

Evaluating a set of potential relations between skills and topics in the knowledge graph, participants pointed out the main following points:

- Linking two skills or topics in the knowledge graph is not a binary process, in which the elements are linked or not, but rather a scaled approach, where the relations have a level of strength (also expressed by some participants as “distance”) between the elements. Relation strength or element distance is influenced by several factors, which include but not limited to: the domain in which they exist, the interpretation of the elements description, and the context of connecting them together.
- Skills and topics are not always directly related to each other. On several occasions, the existence of an intermediate element (or multiple elements) provides more meaningful connection between skills or topics. Utilizing additional leaning content to create a transitive relation between two learning elements is expressed to offer more meaningful connections in the domains of the participants.
- All participants pointed out the importance of considering domain dependencies of the relations. While two educational topics might be strongly relevant in one domain, they might not be as strongly relevant in another. The fact that the two elements are connected (at a certain distance) or not, is less domain dependent as participants highlighted.

- Participants also pointed out that the interpretation of a skill or a topic differs in different domains and different learning contexts. Therefore, concrete and clear definitions of skills or topics is necessary to evaluate the relations among them.

2.3.2. Given the three learner stories, how would you order the following content in three learning paths corresponding to each story?

- To answer this question, participants created different learning paths based on the user stories.
- All participants created an individualized path for each learner.
- Two of the participants pointed out the creation of the learning path for individual learners is not a process that takes place only at the beginning of the learning, but rather a process, in which the path is adjusted and updated as the learner progresses.
- Utilizing existing models for generating learning pathways was also pointed out. An example of those models is the Learning Pathways Grid¹.
- One participant highlighted the role of mentoring in generating more meaningful learning paths, alongside the automatic recommendations. This is because mentoring allows a better understanding of the learner's context, goals, preferences, and leaning needs.
- Participants also addressed that the content of the learning path is not always a mixture of skills and topics. An expert pointed out that:

“When we create the topics, they already come with an order. Usually, we define the concept in the skill (e.g., what is an emotion), and then we go to the "how" of the skill (e.g., how to recognize your emotions)”

This means that according to the approach of creating educational content in the knowledge graph, some of the content should be kept in the same order as defined by the expert.

2.3.3. What are the main factors that you used to select the elements and order of the learning path?

Participants have addressed different approaches for re-ordering the learning path and personalizing its content. A group of factors have been pointed out by the participants to account for the individual learning needs of each learner. Those factors are:

- **Learning goal:** Which is not only the goal that the learners choose on a learning platform, but rather the reason of going through the learning process in the first place.

“... ask the reason why he is doing this. Is his goal based on his own awareness and growth or is it someone else's goal, who has recommended to him that he should improve his knowledge in this area.”

“Some types of individuals will prioritize the solution of the problem, whereas others will become more and more interested in the topic and will keep searching for new content until a state I would expect them to be autonomous.”

¹ <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1609406918791605>

- **Motivation:** The motivation factor has been pointed out to include not only the motive for starting the learning process, but also to continue the learning path till the end. This factor influences the length and content of the learning path, since it might increase the learner's interest in continuing to learn or discourage them from proceeding with the recommended learning path.
- **Learning history:** The previous knowledge of the learner is also an essential part of the reasoning for creating a personalized learning path. Past knowledge includes formal and informal forms of education as well as the skills gained in a practical setting, such as learning-on-the-job.
- **Time available for learning:** Which is a limiting factor that must be considered when suggesting an individual learning path, since the selection of skills and topics in the path might exceed the available time that a learner can dedicate to reach their goal.

One participant pointed out the problem breakdown as an approach that is naturally followed to define the learner's goal, motivation, and urgency of achieving the final step of the learning path. Problem breakdown is a process that depends greatly on the problem description. This can be greatly enhanced through a discussion with the learner, reflecting on the mentoring approach as discussed before.

The previous factors are pointed out to express the context of the learner, completely or partially. As experts consider those factors naturally in creating personalized learning paths, a recommendation system is supposed to account for them as well in a learning platform.

2.3.4. *How do you evaluate the following, automatically generated, learning path?*

In their evaluation of a learning path that was generated automatically, most of the participants found that it does not address the previous points they used in individualizing the path for each learner.

“Here we can see topics from different skills. It starts with goal setting and then goes to the skill of recognizing emotions. Not an obvious move... it would make more sense to go to stress management. After that it goes to emotion regulation (which follows nicely the skill of recognizing emotions) and then stress management and finally resilience (also makes sense).”

Two participants also emphasized the role of considering the original order, which was defined by the content creators, in reconstructing the learning path automatically. This was highlighted on the topic level, rather than the skill level, as mentioned (2.3.2).

3. Focus group on user contextual modelling

3.1. Background

The results of the first evaluations of the knowledge graph and the recommendation algorithm showed that the meaning of the learning context may be understood differently based on the domain of expertise. Therefore, a concrete definition of the learning context and the factors that describe it was an important step to align the contextualization approach in the recommender system with the requirements of the different domains covered in the eDeor platform in general, and especially those that are included in OSCAR project.

To accomplish this goal, a literature survey and a focus group discussion were carried out to define the learning context and its factors in concretely within the scope of OSCAR project. The focus group was conducted with pedagogical experts, to align the context definition from the technical side with learning theories.

Participants of the focus group were contacted through the experts in OSCAR project based on the on-going collaboration on the development of eDeor platform. This meant that the participating experts were familiar with how the eDeor platform works and what the overall goal of the knowledge graph and the recommendation system is.

Demographically, focus group participant were from Germany.

3.2. Methodology

The focus groups were planned and executed according to the following protocol:

- **Participants:** 3 experts.
- **Date and time:** 09.06.2022, 09:00-11:00
- **Duration:** 2:00 hours
- **Pre-requisites:** Pedagogical background, Familiar with OSCAR-related content.
- **Location:** Online (Zoom video conference)
- **Moderator:** Hasan Abu-Rasheed (USI)
- **Digital formats used:** MS-PowerPoint

- **Procedure:**
 1. *Welcome and explanation of the focus group's goal (5 min).*
 2. *Introduction to the literature survey results on context factors in technology enhanced learning (TEL) (15 min):*
Results of the surveyed literature were presented to elaborate the current state of understanding on the context definition and factors from the technical team.
 3. *Discussion on learning context definition and contextual factors in learner profiles (60 min):*
Participant discussed the general adoption of a learning-context definition for online learning platforms, sch as eDeor. Participating experts also discussed the learning theories, where the learning context is relevant. Capturing the learner context has been also discussed, in terms of

defining factors that enable describing that context in a user profile, which can then be used by an algorithm to generate context-aware learning path recommendations.

4. *Summary and final thoughts (10 min).*

• **Questions discussed by the participants:**

1. Is context fundamentally important to the learning process, both in formal and informal learning?
2. In which learning theories is the learning context used?
3. Which context dimensions and factors are relevant in our use case?
4. How are these factors compared (prioritized) in terms of importance?

3.3. Findings

The discussion with the pedagogical experts has revealed important perspectives for context consideration in the learning recommendations. The pedagogical perspective points out user-centric, domain-related, institutional, and environment-related aspects that are necessary for the definition of a learning context.

Expert input on the previous questions can be summarized in the following points:

3.3.1. *Is context fundamentally important to the learning process, both in formal and informal learning?*

- All participants emphasized the important role that learning context plays in the learning process. However, that importance is directly related to the concrete definition of the context and the actors or elements it describes.
- Participants have pointed out that the learning context is not only the one of the learners, but also the one of the learning objects themselves, e.g., learning materials.
- The context of learning objects is domain dependent and differs for the same object in different settings.
- The last two points mean that the context is basically not only attached to an entity (user or learning object) but rather appears in the connections between those entities. In other words, the learning context can only be described when two or more entities interact with each other. This interaction can be, for example, between two learning objects that are taught together in a certain situation, or between a learner and the material they need to learn in a certain situation.

3.3.2. *In which learning theories is the learning context used and how is it realized?*

- Participants have pointed out the consideration of context in the situated and subject-oriented learning theories.
- The context is realized through a set of factors that describe the connections between the entities involved in a learning process.

- Participants also pointed out that context is not defined the same ways in all those theories, due to its dependency on aspects like the domain and the format of education (formal, informal, etc.).
- An overarching definition can be, however, drawn to combine the main features of each context definition, and allow at the same time for a margin for tailoring the definition to the domain's requirements. This definition can be phrased as:

Learning Context is defined as the situation, in which learning happens, which includes the learner's situation (location, previous knowledge, etc.) and the learning object's situation (type, length, implementation scenario, etc.).

3.3.3. Which context dimensions and factors are relevant in our use case?

Participants have examined the contextual factors surveyed in the literature, and the ones defined in the previous focus groups, including the learning goal, learner's previous knowledge, time, motivation, etc. While all those factors were meaningful to the pedagogical experts, they pointed out that:

- the interpretation of the contextual factor should be made carefully, considering the domain- and environment-dependency. Such aspects influence the relation between the elements of a learning path, and the relation between each element and the learner.
- On an online learning platform, not all contextual factors can be determined. Therefore, the context should be addressed in the light of factors that are collectable from the learner. Other contextual factors usually require a human intervention to collect and identify, which is then a process that mentoring of the learning platform may resolve. This limitation should be addressed in the contextual description of learning materials, learners, and the relations between them.

3.3.4. How are these factors compared (prioritized) in terms of importance?

- Experts have pointed out that there is not one order of importance for all contextual factors. The reason is that the domain dependency and the institutional and environmental factors play an essential role in considering one contextual factor (or a group of them) more relevant to the learner than others.
- For that reason, it is important that the contextualization of the learning path recommendation considers factors that apply for multiple domains and apply to different user groups. Other factors that vary based on, e.g. institutional aspects, can be either addressed in a more complex system, or better by a human element in the learning loop, e.g. a mentor.

4. Focus Groups on knowledge graph and recommender system evaluation

4.1. Background

The first two focus groups took place at the beginning of the second phase in OSCAR project, where the concepts of building the knowledge graph and the recommender system were at their early stages of implementation. The last focus group, on the other hand, has been conducted as a part of the evaluation framework for the technical development of the knowledge graph and recommendation algorithm. The input to this focus group was the resulting systems and data structures, which were further developed and enhanced based on the output of the first two focus groups.

Knowledge graph and recommender system evaluation focus groups were planned to include both user types of the eDeor platform: content creators and learners. Therefore, two separate focus groups were planned for that evaluation, with a tailored focus on the points that are most important for each type of users. The topics covered in the focus group with content creators included the knowledge graph and the recommendation algorithm alike, while the focus group planned with learners had a focus on the recommendation system only, since the learner has little interest in the database structure and is directly influenced by the learning path recommendation.

The focus group with experts and content creators was conducted in the second year of OSCAR project. The focus group with learners was conducted in the third project year. Participants in both focus groups were recruited through the project partner ULB, based on their field of expertise in curriculum building and training program design for researchers. Their background intersects greatly with the topics covered in OSCAR project on researcher mental health and career development. Learners group included early career researchers, who are the main target group for OSCAR project.

Participants in the focus groups had no previous interaction with eDoer as a learning platform, or the algorithms used for the recommendation and graph construction. A total of 6 participants took a part in the expert focus group. Participants were demographically from the Czech Republic, Portugal, Belgium, Switzerland, and Norway. In the learner focus group included 5 participants, from Belgium and Norway. In the following, the procedure and results of the expert- and learner focus groups are described in detail.

4.2. Expert FG Methodology

The focus groups were planned and executed according to the following protocol:

- **Participants:** 6 experts
- **Date and time:** 20.12.2022, 13:00-17:00
- **Duration:** 4:00 hours
- **Pre-requisites:** experience in OSCAR-related field
- **Location:** Online (MS-Teams video conference)
- **Moderators:** Hasan Abu-Rasheed (USI), Mathias Schroijsen (ULB)
- **Digital formats used:** MS-PowerPoint
- **Procedure:**

1. *Welcome (10min)*: Focus Group Leaders will welcome the group, present themselves and ask for a quick presentation of each person in the group (e.g. name, institution and field of study).
 2. *Quick presentation of the OSCAR project (5min)*:
Focus Group Leaders will briefly present the OSCAR project and explain the objectives of the focus group that is happening.
 3. *Quick presentation of the knowledge graph and the recommender logic (15min)*:
Focus group leaders will introduce the concept of the knowledge graph in the eDoer system, and briefly explain the path recommendation strategy(s).
 4. *Discussion on the Knowledge Graph (90min)*:
The group will answer the KG questions below. Each question will be discussed for 30 min
 5. *Break (20min)*.
 6. *Discussion on the Graph based path recommendation (90min)*:
The group will answer the recommendation algorithm questions below. Each question will be discussed for 30 min.
 7. *Gather up (15min)*:
Collect and summarize the main points, opinions and requirements discussed in the workshop.
 8. *Close-up (5min)*:
Close the session and ask for a take-away word/message that will be collected using a word cloud collection software.
- **Questions discussed by the participants:**
 - **Knowledge graph questions:**
 1. Could multiple learning goals be semantically linked to each other? And if they could, should they?
 2. What metadata could be used to find similarities between the learning elements of two learning goals and how?
 3. How can the learning context be represented in the description of the learning material and the KG structure?
 - **Recommender System questions:**
 1. When does the recommender system have to recommend all content from one learning goal and when does it recommend a part of the content, and why?
 2. Is the recommended learning path able to combine learning materials to enable solving a real-world problem, i.e. in a real context?
 3. How do you define the learning context in your domain, and what is essential to be considered by the algorithm, to account for that context?

4.3. Expert FG Findings

Discussion of the knowledge graph and recommendation algorithm has shown in general a great interest from the participants in the concepts of linked educational data and intelligent decision making algorithms. A part of the reason for that interest as explained by some of the participants is their involvement in researcher training programs on transferrable skills, which are usually connected to

different domains and appear in different contexts. Therefore, the ability of an automated system to support the content creator and learner alike in addressing this type of skills is found beneficial.

The participants answers and input on the focus group questions can be summarized in the following points:

4.3.1. Could multiple learning goals be semantically linked to each other? And if they could, should they?

- All participants have agreed that connecting competencies and learning goals (along with their courses and topics) to each other is very useful, since the learners may not know exactly what they need to learn. Therefore, a learning path that is composed of elements from multiple learning goals is important in such situations.
- Participants also addressed the cases where learners are capable of describing their learning need but not having their learning goal as one journey in the system, but rather distributed on multiple journeys, which then could be combined for the learner in the learning path.
- In the domain of transferrable skills, the separation of learning goals is not preferred. Therefore, the combination of those goals in one overall learning goal is a better approach for the content creators and learners.
- Participants pointed out that in the case of transferrable skills, the data model should also highlight the transferability of certain courses, to utilize them in multiple learning goals and in multiple contexts.
- Participants also pointed out the importance of the connections between learning contents in different languages, which allows reaching more options for the learning materials, especially for learners that are bilingual.

4.3.2. What metadata could be used to find similarities between the learning elements of two learning goals and how?

- Participants highlighted that it is important for the content creators and automated systems to collaborate on creating the metadata that describes educational materials and allow a better relation extraction.
- Meta-data needed to enhance relation extraction has considerable time- and effort-requirements to create comprehensive textual descriptions of the content.
- Participants also expressed that automating the process of creating textual content to describe the learning materials can help the system in getting closer to a unified description methodology, which may enhance the similarity between learning materials.
- It is important for the experts, however, that the descriptions are monitored and evaluated by the content creators, to ensure that the context is reflected clearly and correctly in it.
- The collaboration between algorithms and content creators to create meta-data for the materials can be enhanced if the algorithms support content creators in finding out how it deduces the semantics from their own content description. This will make it clearer to the expert how to phrase the descriptions of learning materials, to enable better relation extraction.

- Another approach suggested for enhancing the descriptions of educational content is clustering of material descriptions and using keyword suggestions.
- Another participant mentioned that using the same keywords may be partially also scaled, to reflect the level of relevance of each keyword to the content.

4.3.3. How can the learning context be represented in the description of the learning material and the KG structure?

- Participants have addressed that the context is a complex aspect that is not only represented in the material's metadata. However, that description is still important to reflect the part of the context, in which the material should appear in the learning process.
- Participants also addressed that there are general learning situations, in which all learners should be offered a certain learning material, as well as other learning situations where the personalization is needed. To address this issue, the participants suggested that context metadata may include two parts, a general and more specific one, where the latter is used in contextualizing the recommendations.
- A participant highlighted the role of using the keyword approach to represent the context of a learning material.
- Participants pointed out that the knowledge graph itself can be used to show the clusters of courses and topics, which reflects the context of a learning material.

4.3.4. When does the recommender system have to recommend all content from one learning goal and when does it recommend a part of the content, and why?

The answer to this question has divided the participants equally into two main groups:

- The first group found that the content creator includes materials for different contexts and target users in a learning journey they are designing. If the content creator describes those target groups and their contexts clearly, the recommendation system should be able to make an automated decision to select the learning elements that are suitable to an individual learner.
- The second group of participants, although it agrees that content creators describe a context for their educational materials, still finds that:

“Offering all the potential paths to the learners will help those who are able to choose a suitable learning path for themselves to participate in the selection process, supported by the automated recommendation.”

In other words, the recommender may select only a part of the materials in a journey, but should still offer an overview on all potential paths and available materials, to support the learners who can self-direct their learning process.

- Participants of the second group argue that the ability to enable the learner to include more content or see the “bigger picture” at any time of the learning can be very useful, and may account for the development of the learner's context and ability to choose for themselves the rest of the recommended path.

- Showing multiple recommendations for the learner can be essential in some domains and for some learner groups, since the learners are also responsible naturally for choosing what they should learn, such as PhD students.
- Participants also pointed out that the style of creating journey in the system greatly influences the answer to this question, which means that the content creator should also be aware of the fact that the algorithm may (or may not) select only a part of the content they created for personalizing the recommendations.
- In response to those points, participants of the first group argue that the role of the learner's preference to explore the graph or to go directly to the final goal is essential, especially for some learner backgrounds or fields of study. This means that showing all the content or a part of it should be based on the learner's exploration preference, and eventually considered in the recommendation itself.
- The first group argument continues to point out that recommendations can also be progressive, in the sense that a learning path may be adjusted based on the progress of the learner.

4.3.5. *Is the recommended learning path able to combine learning materials to enable solving a real-world problem, i.e. in a real context?*

- Participants mentioned that: since learners may have different interests, some of which are focused, and others may want to explore more content, recommending the learning path helps the learner to notice the different combinations of learning elements they need for the learning goal, which is a problem that mentors usually support learners in solving.
- The recommendation from multiple learning goals is essential in the cases where learners may not be able to describe their needs or summarize those needs in one learning goal.
- Path recommendation becomes essential in transitioning from one field to another, such as transitioning from academia to industry, where the learning goals are not summarized in overall one, but rather a collection of partial goals that can be combined in the recommended path to solve that issue.
- Participants also pointed out that this combination of elements from different learning goals may result in a problem, if they include repetitive content.

“Connecting educational content from different experts that is very similar may cause the algorithms to recommend repetitive content for learners.”

4.3.6. *How do you define the learning context in your domain, and what is essential to be considered by the algorithm, to account for that context?*

- Participants pointed out that they rely on specific indicators or factors that help them recommend a personalized learning path for their students and clients.
- While some of those factors are greatly dependent on the domain of the expert, majority of the participants pointed out similar factors that are considered across their domains. Those cross-domain factors include: the learning goal, motivation, and time factors.

- Other factors highlighted by the participants in their respective domains are:
 - **Level of proficiency:** Which reflect the experience and previous knowledge the learner has.
 - **Phase of learning:** which indicates being at the beginning of the degree of study, or at the end of it, where e.g. the degree manuscript is due for submission. The latter case indicated that a higher level of stress is usually considered in suggesting a learning path.
 - **Motivation:** which is an important contextual factor in generating the recommendation, because it influences the learner's continuation of the recommended path till the end.
 - **Time:** is highlighted as a decisive factor for some learner groups
 - **Language:** of the learning material and multilingualism, especially for bilingual learners.
 - **Learning goal:** which greatly affects the elements of any suggested learning path and the order of those elements.
- Participants also emphasized the role of mentors and supervisors in validating the recommended learning paths for certain groups of learners, as long as an access to a mentor is available.

4.4. Learner FG Methodology

The focus groups were planned and executed according to the following protocol:

- **Participants:** 5 experts
- **Date and time:** 21.04.2023, 15:00-17:00
- **Duration:** 2:00 hours
- **Pre-requisites:** None
- **Location:** Online (MS-Teams video conference)
- **Moderators:** Hasan Abu-Rasheed (USI), Mathias Schroijsen (ULB)
- **Digital formats used:** MS-PowerPoint
- **Procedure:**
 9. *Welcome (5min):* Focus Group Leaders will welcome the group, present themselves and ask for a quick presentation of each person in the group (e.g. name, institution and field of study).
 10. *Quick presentation of the OSCAR project (5min):*
Focus Group Leaders will briefly present the OSCAR project and explain the objectives of the focus group that is happening.
 11. *Quick presentation of the knowledge graph and the recommender logic (10min):*
Focus group leaders will introduce the concept of the knowledge graph-based recommender in the eDoer system, and the path recommendation strategies.
 12. *Hands on testing of the graph-based recommender system (60min):*

The group will test the system using the eDoer experimental platform, by creating user profiles and evaluating the resulting recommendations.

13. *Discussion on the Graph based path recommendation (30min):*

The group will answer the recommendation algorithm questions below. Each question will be discussed for 10 min.

14. *Gather up (5min):*

Collect and summarize the main points, opinions and requirements discussed in the group.

15. *Close-up (5min):*

Close the session and ask for a take-away word/message that will be collected using a word cloud collection software.

- **Questions discussed by the participants:**

- ***Recommender System questions:***

1. Is the explorative recommendation strategy useful in your context and why?
2. How can exploring different learning trajectories and their interrelation be useful to you?
3. Is the recommendation logic able to combine learning materials for you that correspond well to your context?

4.5. Learner FG Findings

The discussion with the learners in this focus group confirmed the results of the previous groups and highlighted new perspective to the learner needs from the recommendation algorithm. Learner came from different backgrounds, which allowed the observation of the recommender performance from different points of view. This was especially important in the cases where the selected learning goal was selected by different users, to compare and discuss the differences in the recommended learning path.

The participants answers and input on the focus group questions can be summarized in the following points:

4.5.1. *Is the explorative recommendation strategy useful in your context and why?*

- All participants agreed that connecting competencies, learning goals, courses, and topics, is useful to them. This is partially due to the fact that the problems they face are usually complex in real life and require information from different learning domains.
- The participants highlighted that the recommendation strategy should also be clear to the learner. This is because some of the recommended elements may not be expected by the learner but may still be relevant to their needs. The learner, however, will not consider studying this part of the recommendation without understanding why it was recommended.
- Participants highlighted that although the strategy of connecting elements from different domains and learning goals is useful, the ability of the recommender to explore more content is still limited in the current recommender by the explicit selection of the learning goal. Other content may still be relevant but it requires the learner to adjust their learning goal selection to reach that additional materials.

4.5.2. *How can exploring different learning trajectories and their interrelation be useful to you?*

- Being from different backgrounds, the participants agreed that when they request a recommendation from the system for the same learning goal, they expect a personalized path that is closer to their domain, even though it has learning objects from other domains. The visibility of the intersections between the potential learning paths (learning trajectories) is also useful to inform the learner of other exploration potentials they can take advantage of.
- Some of the participants also highlighted here that exploring the potential learning paths and their intersections is a task that requires time and understanding of the system. This means that the system should offer elements (e.g., visualizations) to support this exploration during the learning.
- As learners, the participants emphasized that the exploration, awareness of potential learning elements on other paths, and the awareness of the system logic, is essential to have agency over the decision to follow the recommendation and commit to the learning time needed.

4.5.3. *Is the recommendation logic able to combine learning materials for you that correspond well to your context?*

- Participants have answered this question based on the hands-on testing of the recommender. They highlighted promising points and limitations in the recommendations they received.
- Majority of the participants received content in the recommended path that was not expected but useful to their learning goal, which was a positive addition to the learning materials they expected to be recommended. This additional content was a result of the connection between the learning goals on the graphical database, which the recommender uses.
- 3 of the participants highlighted that the role of changing the user-context fields in the user profile was only noticeable when the change is considerably big. Small changes did not reflect on the recommended path.
- Participants also pointed out that the selection of the learning goal is in itself was an essential method they used to change the recommended path, since there are multiple learning goals in the database with similar wording of the names. This point was particularly important because the recommendation system requires a clear definition of the learning goal, and therefore was an input that we used to further enhance the recommendation algorithm, taking into account the goal selection process, not only the definition of the user context.
- Participants also highlighted that the interface elements, which they use to search for a learning goal in the system, are important to enable the learner to find the correct goal they need. For example, the learner might consider adding multiple learning goals, instead of only one as the current version allows. This, in turn, is meant to enhance the goal setting from the learner side, and thus the recommended path.